

THE RESIGNIFICATION OF SUPERVISED INTERNSHIP IN TEACHER EDUCATION: THE INTERNSHIP FIELD AS A CONCRETE REALITY

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Abstract: This article deals with teacher education in Geography and problematizes the need to overcome the dichotomous perspective of the internship as a practical activity to the detriment of a theoretical corpus. The objective of this work is to propose a reflection on the construction of a new identity for the supervised internship activity from its resignification through the understanding of the internship field as a concrete reality. Among the authors that make up our theoretical construct are: Thiollent (1986), Libâneo (1990), Vasconcelos (2002), Pimenta e Lima (2006), Stefanello (2009), among others. The methodology used was the bibliographic research articulated the action research. The results obtained demonstrate the need to approach the teaching with the school reality and the student himself as a concrete subject. From this perspective, positive results are observed with the proposition of a teaching-learning project based on elements of the reality experienced by the student regarding the construction of meaningful learning for both students and teachers in training.

Keywords: Teacher training. Geography Teaching. Internship field.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the premise that "knowing consists of constructing and reconstructing the object of knowledge, in order to apprehend the mechanism of this construction" (MENDONÇA; KOZEL, 2002, p. 192), the Supervised Internship of Teacher Training provides an opportunity to work on the interface between practical development and theoretical deepening. Process in which theory and practice are articulated all the time (LIBÂNEO, 1990, p. 27).

The supervised internship is a complex and significant formative activity in teacher education" (SOUZA, 2013, p. 108), not consisting only in the traditional phases of observation, planning and conducting, as there are a range of nuances to be apprehended in the school space.

From this perspective, a change in values and beliefs constructed historically is necessary, bearing in mind that the internship is a field of knowledge, and as such, has an epistemological statute that denies it the simple reduction to instrumental practical activity, and should be constituted in the dialectical relationship between training courses and the social field (PIMENTA; LIMA, 2006).

That said, this article, which deals with teacher training in Geography and discusses the need to overcome the dichotomous perspective of the internship as a practical activity to the detriment of a theoretical *corpus*, aims to propose a reflection on the construction of a new identity for the activity supervised internship based on the redefinition of this practice through the understanding of the internship field as a concrete reality.

The discussion proposed here is based on the supervised internship experience of the Licentiate in Geography course at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte, held in the semester of 2021.2 with a 9th grade class of Elementary School at the Professor José Fernandes Machado State School, located in the neighborhood from Ponta Negra – Natal/RN.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Souza (2013, p. 111) apprehends the school "as a concrete spatiality of society". In this perspective, one of the main commitments of teachers in training is to know their future field of work, which translates into terms of a perceptive journey made possible by the activities developed in the supervised internship.

For Sato and Fornel (2011, p. 53), "knowing the organization of the school space and the relationships between subjects is a necessity, insofar as the class is not an isolated event in a room, but is inserted in the space of an educational institution". Thus, observing the school as an institution and a dynamic social organism will enable the intern to gain knowledge, even if limited in view of the complexity of the school environment and the diversity of its subjects, of the general context of the school.

This approximation between observation and observed, object of research and researcher, makes it possible for the interns to perceive in the training process that the students and all the individuals that make up the school community form a diverse group, with different visions and experiences of mute that cohabit the same space and build a school environment that is both singular and plural.

For Vasconcelos (2002, p. 104), the analysis of reality is "an investigative effort [...] in the sense of capturing and understanding reality, as it is in the present, its historical articulation,

in view of its transformation ". Thus, starting from the premise that learning depends on the uniqueness of the learners, on the lived experiences, motivations and interests (ZABALA, 1998), and that "knowledge of the student's reality is essential to subsidize the planning process in a dialectical perspective , [in which] we must take into account the real, flesh-and-blood student who is effectively in the classroom" (VASCONCELOS, 2002, p. 107), we look into the subjects of the educational institution and the school reality in in order to reframe our practice as interns and future teachers.

In short, knowledge of the school reality and our student body will make it possible to propose and carry out interventions that are meaningful for these students, favoring their training as transforming agents of their own reality to the detriment of an empty schooling focused only on quantitative results, because, as Cortella exposes (1997, p. 103):

There is no knowledge that can be apprehended and recreated if it does not deal, initially, with the concerns that people have; it is nonsense to assume that children and young people can be taught, mainly, without starting from the concerns they have, because, otherwise, it will only be achieved (constrained and without interest) the knowledge that should be appropriated (made their own) .

In short, the specialized literature points out that the distancing of the syllabus in relation to the students' experience is, in a way, responsible for part of the students' lack of interest in the classes.

METHODOLOGY

This research is characterized as an action-research, "understood as a form of investigation based on a collective self-reflection undertaken by a given social group in a given space-time context, with the aim of improving their own practices" (SILVA, 2021, p. 9). According to Thiollent (1986, p. 14), action research can be defined as

A type of empirically based social research that is conceived and carried out in close association with an action or the resolution of a collective problem, and in which researchers and participants representative of the situation or problem are involved in a cooperative or participatory way.

Thus, among the methodological procedures used, we have bibliographical, documental and empirical research associated with action research. Bibliographic research based on authors

who contribute to the proposed reflection, including: Thiollent (1986), Libâneo (1990), Cortella (1997), Vasconcelos (2002), Pimenta e Lima (2006), Stefanello (2009), Souza (2013), among others. Documentary through the analysis of documents that regulate basic education in the country and in the teaching institution, such as the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) and the Political Pedagogical Project (PPP) of the school.

However, bearing in mind that the learning process tends to occur from the student's interest and enthusiasm for the content (STEFANELLO, 2009), the proposal is based on the adoption of a teaching-learning project aimed at the student's reality from the use of alternative teaching materials, which, in addition to facilitating the visualization of the subjects addressed in the classroom and providing the integration of all students, allow them to think, reflect and become interested in the topics discussed in the course program (FLORES *et al.* 2010, p. 4-5).

D Among the resources and languages used to work on the syllabus in the classroom are maps, prints, *folders*, short documentaries, mental maps, *quizzes*, games, poems, songs and parodies, which, being essentially cultural elements, when transposed as didactic materials tend to bring teachers closer to the students' everyday language, thus facilitating the learning relationship. However, Flores *et al.* (2010) points out that the use of these materials cannot be disconnected from planning and teaching evaluation work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to Vasconcelos (2002, p. 108), "learning does not occur in the void, in the abstract, in a world apart, but on the contrary, in a given context, in a given reality, whether one contemplates the classroom itself, the school, as well as the immediate community, or even society as a whole". Therefore, as there is an intrinsic relationship between education and the political-socio-economic-cultural system, teachers need to reflect on the general school context in which they will work.

From this perspective, our internship field is the Professor José Fernandes Machado State School, located at Avenida Muriu Beach, in the neighborhood of Ponta Negra, south of the city of Natal/RN. The educational institution, created in the beginning of the 80's through Decree nº 8.531 of 11/09/82 of the State government, currently operates in Basic Education with the Elementary, Middle and Vocational Technical levels.

In the context of our work as interns, we accompanied a 9th grade elementary school class, and when we looked at the subjects of the Escola Campo do Internship, we found that the institution's students are mostly from the Vila de Ponta Negra, which is located if about 3 km

from the school. Henceforth, we observe that due to the socioeconomic context in which they are inserted, many of the students of the institution have to contribute with the domestic chores at home or even work outside the home to help with the family income. Therefore, social difficulties reverberate in school difficulties and students have been having their learning capacity impaired in all disciplinary contents, not only in terms of Geography.

In view of the analysis of student performance in previous years, in external assessments such as Provinha Brasil, Prova Brasil and SAEB, learning difficulties were identified, especially with regard to reading, writing, interpretation and calculation skills. In addition to this aspect, high rates of school dropout were also observed, which permeates not only the issue of learning, but also the unequal socioeconomic context in which the school's students are inserted.

In general terms, the educational institution largely serves young people from Vila de Ponta Negra, a community made up mainly of fishermen and self-employed professionals, as well as foreign students of different nationalities, forming an environment of contrasts, not only in terms of its location, since the community surrounding the institution has a high purchasing power, but also the public served by the school, which demands a differentiated effort to work with this sociocultural diversity.

With regard to the school community, there is a gap between the School, the family and the students, as there is a gap between the leaders and other employees of the students, contributing to a more hierarchical and distanced view, which may stimulate disinterest and non-positive behavioral actions on the part of students, considering that "the way students act is a direct reflection of the way they are treated, [...] [making them feel excluded]" (SILVA, 2019, p. 14).

In addition, it appears that the students' parents do not participate much in the school's daily life and in the actions promoted by the school itself, such as cultural activities within the school calendar. However, to what extent can we consider this attitude as disinterest when economic needs are acute and those responsible face an exhausting daily work routine in search of their family's survival?

Regarding the physical and structural space of the institution, the school has a total area of 36,600m², with 3,587m² of built area, with its dependencies formed by five built masonry blocks. Each respective block has its own conformation, namely: the school's administrative area, where the direction, coordination, secretariat, teachers' room, multimedia room, library, bathrooms and storeroom are located; the refectory, with the kitchen and the school yard; and the other three blocks where the 27 classrooms are located, one of which is where the auditorium and the computer room are located (SILVA, 2019).

The school also has an indoor sports court; uncovered patio; green area; broadband internet access, electricity and water from the public network, filtered water, school meals for students, periodic garbage collection and septic tank. Among the equipment available at the institution we have: TV, DVD and stereo; copy machine; printer and multimedia projector (*datashow*).

However, the school has some difficulties that need to be solved in terms of learning (high dropout and repetition rates); security (to prevent the entry of strangers who take advantage of the existence of low walls) and infrastructure (maintenance of the water tank, need for roofing and combating termite infestation, lack of access for people with special needs, inadequacies in the school lunch storage deposit, school air conditioning, increased number of drinking fountains, among others) (GOVERNMENT OF THE STATE OF RIO GRANDE DO NORTE, 2019).

Faced with the problem at hand, we, as interns, developed a teaching-learning project in geography based on the reality of our students, and after reflecting on the reality of the school, its subjects and infrastructure, the methodological path chosen was the adoption of different languages in the practices proposed to work with the globalization theme, which was the demand pointed out by the internship supervisor and professor of Geography at the institution.

In this way, following the BNCC, which is one of the normative documents of Brazilian Education, when working with the thematic unit World of Work, which has as its premise the development of competences and abilities EF09GE02, EF09GE05 and EF09GE11, in which students should be able to analyze facts and situations to understand world integration by comparing different interpretations and economic, cultural and environmental dynamics (BRASIL, 2018), we seek to bring elements of the student's reality and work with globalization from the spatial elements with which they live daily, global tourism, large *shopping malls* and multinational *fast-food restaurants* that permeate the Ponta Negra neighborhood, business buildings that are a symbol of financial/business capital and the contrasts between the neighborhood and Vila de Ponta Negra, which reflect the unequal integration of these territorial portions in the globalization process.

These questions were worked through the analysis of songs by local authors, *folders* that introduce elements of the Ponta Negra neighborhood to the discussion about globalization, the construction of mental maps, games, among other alternative didactic products. Some of the materials used and produced by the interns can be seen in Figure 01, which brings a synthetic mosaic of the materials worked on during the interventions carried out with this theme.

Figure 1 - Mosaic of teaching materials produced and used by interns

Source: Elaboration of the author (2022)

In general terms, it appears that during the implementation of the teaching-learning project, students became more active in Geography classes, collaborating with interns by

providing examples of their reality for discussions on globalization, in addition to increasing the frequency in classes and carrying out the required activities.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

There are many conceptions about the role of the internship in teacher training, many of the current perspectives lead towards a dichotomy between theory and practice, defining the internship as a practical moment of a professional training course. This view, sometimes reductionist, contributes to the devaluation of theoretical knowledge in favor of a practice for the sake of practice.

In this perspective, it was necessary to reframe the internship activity with consequent overcoming of the view of the activity as a practical exercise based on observation and conducting. Other paths must be adopted, and bearing in mind that Geography in Elementary Education must start from the local reality of the subjects, the introduction of elements of the students' experience in classroom discussions proves to be an assertive path for the construction of meaningful learning, proving to be a valid proposition also with regard to greater student involvement with activities carried out in the classroom.

In short, as interns seeking to re-signify our practices and the supervised internship itself, we try to get to know our students, understand the reality in which they are inserted and from the apprehended scenario, even if our understanding is more superficial in the face of the complexity of the reality experienced. For each student, we work with a proposal that starts from the school floor, from the school reality to the academy, and not the other way around. The teaching-learning project takes place in a context of exchanges that are based on mutual cooperation, students and teachers building together knowledge in an integrated way and no longer fragmented between theory and practice.

Thus, the results obtained demonstrate the need to bring the teaching practice closer to the school reality and the student himself as a concrete subject. It appears that the proposition of the teaching-learning project on globalization, based on elements of the reality experienced by the student and the adoption of different languages, is a viable alternative to be implemented, with positive results regarding the construction of a learning process. Significant for both students and teachers in training, in addition to having contributed to greater student involvement in Geography classes during the period it was held.

REFERENCES

BRAZIL. Ministry of Education. **Common National Curriculum Base**. Brasilia, 2018.

CORTELLA, MS **School and knowledge**: reflection on the epistemological and political foundations of this relationship. 1997. Thesis (Doctorate in Education) - Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo, São Paulo, 1997.

FLORES, BO *et al.* Didactic materials: alternatives to the practice of geography. **Anais do XVI National Meeting of Geographers**. UFRGS: Porto Alegre, 2010. Available at: <http://www.eng2018.agb.org.br/>. Accessed on: 08 Feb. 2022.

GOVERNMENT OF THE STATE OF RIO GRANDE DO NORTE. Secretary of State for Education and Culture. **Pedagogical Political Project**: Professor José Fernandes Vasconcelos State School. Christmas, 2019.

LIBÂNEO, JC **Didactic**. São Paulo: Editora Cortez, 1990.

MENDONÇA, FA; KOZEL, S. **Elements of the epistemology of contemporary geography**. Curitiba: UFPR, 2002.

PIMENTA, SG; LIMA, MSL Internship and teaching: different conceptions. **Póiesis Magazine**, v. 3, no. 3, p. 5-24, 2006. Available at: <http://www.revistas.ufg.br/poiesis/article/view/10542/7012>. Accessed on: 03 Feb. 2022.

SATO, ECM; FORNEL, SR The knowledge of the school space. *In*: PASSINI, EY; PASSINI, R.; MALYSZ, ST (Eds.). **Geography teaching practice and supervised internship**. 2 ed. São Paulo: Context, 2011, p. 52-57.

SILVA, AB Reorganization and reconnection of knowledge: teacher training and teaching practices in Geography. **Cocar Magazine**, Belém, v. 15, no. 33, p. 1-18, 2021. Available at: <https://periodicos.uepa.br/index.php/cocar/article/view/4660>. Accessed on: 02 Feb. 2022.

SILVA, ME **Reflective internship report**: Professor José Fernandes Machado State School (Machadão). Discipline of Supervised Internship for Teacher Training. Christmas, 2019.

SOUZA, VC de. Challenges of the supervised internship in the training of geography teachers. *In*: ALBUQUERQUE, MAM de; FERREIRA, JAS (Org.). **Training, research and teaching practices**: curricular reforms in question. João Pessoa: Mídia, 2013, p. 105-130.

STEFANELLO, AC **Didactics and evaluation of learning in Geography teaching**. Curitiba: Ibpex. 2009.

THIOLLENT, M. **Action research methodology**. 2 ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 1986.

VASCONCELOS, CS **Planning**: teaching-learning project and political-pedagogical project. 10 ed. São Paulo: Libertad, 2002, P. 95-151.

ZABALA, A. **Educational practice**: how to teach? Porto Alegre: ArtMed, 1998, p. 27-86.